

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Xayrullo Rizayev

ONA TILI FANLARINI O'QITISHDA LOYIHA METODINING

AHAMİYATI VA DOLZARBLIGI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/IYUN

